

FIT4FOOD2030

Towards FOOD 2030 - Future-proofing the European food systems through research & innovation

Deliverable 9.2

Project Execution Handbook

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1. Introduction

FIT4FOOD2030 has been established to support the European Commission (EC) in the development and implementation of the [FOOD2030](#) policy framework and its action plan. This Coordination and Support Action (CSA) aims to establish a sustainable multi-stakeholder, multi-level platform, mobilizing a wide variety of stakeholders at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe; the FOOD 2030 Platform. The project will support the urgently needed transformation of research and innovation (R&I) on food and nutrition security (FNS) by providing a network and instruments for the adoption of a food system and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach to R&I.

To support the strategic coordination and overall management structure of this project, a Project Execution Handbook (PEH) is essential. It is a source of reference for all members of the consortium and defines the internal processes for securing a successful completion of the project.

This PEH starts with a short description of the project, including project design and a description of the work packages (WPs) as well as the different phases of the project (Chapter 2). Subsequently, the project's organizational and management structures are outlined (Chapter 3). Chapter 4 provides an overview of deliverables and milestones in chronological order as well as a general description of the deliverable review procedure, as part of quality control. Chapter 5 refers to the risk registry which will be developed by the VU in collaboration with all consortium partners. Legal aspects are described in Chapter 6, including references to the Grant Agreement (EU GA), and the Consortium Agreement (CA). Chapter 7 describes the regulations and requirements with regard to the internal and external communication within the project, whereas Chapter 8 gives an overview of regulations regarding meetings and reporting. Finally, Chapter 9 describes regulations and rules regarding disseminations of results and Open Access.

The general principles for the project execution are defined in the EU GA, the Description of the action (DoA) and the CA. The PEH does not replace any of these established agreements, nor does it replace any of the EU guidelines for project implementation and documentation. Where there are any inconsistencies between these documents, the following order of precedence should be applied: EU GA including DoA Annex 1; CA; PEH (present document). In addition, this document provides standardization of various elements of the project resulting in effective and efficient administration.

This document is a living document. There will be continuous updates to improve the internal processes.

See **Appendix 1** for an overview of relevant abbreviations and acronyms.

2. Project Design and Work Packages

2.1 Project Design

A structured and stepwise project design will be used to build the FOOD 2030 Platform, including four phases.

Phase 1: Actor identification & mobilisation, visioning and system understanding (months 1-12). This phase aims to identify and mobilise relevant actors, unite visions, and increase understanding of barriers and opportunities for transforming the current food system.

- The project first establishes the EU Think Tank, 'Policy Labs' and 'City Labs' with training provided on setting up an effective Community of Practice (CoP).
- Simultaneously an actor analysis will be conducted identifying the stakeholders that must be involved in the transformation of the food system including the identification of groups that are underrepresented in the existing networks but who can have an essential contribution. The actor analysis will be carried out recurrently in order to ensure that the stakeholder group always includes all those who can voice relevant opinions.
- The EU Think Tank, Policy Labs and/or City Labs will also involve the different stakeholders in a process of shared vision development and a process of system understanding; identifying the underlying barriers to the realisation of the vision and enablers that support it.

Phase 2: Developing roadmaps (months 10-16). In this phase, transformation agendas will be developed by exploring and identifying trends, showcases and potential breakthroughs in food systems R&I. Activities take place successively within the City Labs, Policy Labs and EU Think Tank. Showcases are initiatives that have positively affected the food system. The criteria that are important for a successful showcase will also be analysed. Assessing their characteristics, success factors and contributory conditions will result in criteria for best practices. A potential breakthrough is an achievement that may impact the food system significantly in the future. The identification of critical success factors for these roadmaps will aid in the formulation of actionable transformation agendas.

Phase 3: Action planning and training (months 16-36). In this phase the transformation agendas will be put into practice. Policy labs will organize workshops to bring the regional/national stakeholders together, to work towards alignment of R&I policies and programmes within the framework of the transformation agenda. Each Policy Lab may focus on a different objective, depending on the particular setting. In City Labs, prototypes will be developed of (in)formal trainings for different target groups. The experiences of the Policy Labs and City Labs will be discussed within the EU Think Tank, and used as an input for further strategy development.

Phase 4: Scaling up & continuity (months 26-36). The project starts with 7 Policy Labs and 7 City Labs across Europe in year 1, and expands to 10 Policy Labs and 14 City Labs throughout the project. The initial 5 Policy Labs, 7 City Labs and the EU Think Tank form the inner circle. The outer circle of 'followers' is developed during the later stages of the project. In addition, FIT4FOOD2030 will develop instruments (guidelines and tools) which will be distributed through existing R&I policy collaboration initiatives. Instruments include guidelines on how to identify and mobilize actors, mapping exercises on trends, showcases and breakthroughs, alignment of policies, competences training and raising awareness.

2.2 Work Packages: activities and interaction

In order to achieve the objectives during the four phases described, the project is structured into 9 WPs (Table 1) that interact with each other (Figure 1).

Table 1. Work packages and objectives.

WP	WP title	Objectives
WP1	Methodology to build the FOOD2030 Platform	To develop and guide the overall methodology for the creation of the FOOD 2030 Platform by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing and instigating a network approach for a multi-actor, multi-level, transformative network; • Designing and adapting methodologies for multi-stakeholder dialogue and collaboration in the different phases; • Connecting the CoPs within the FOOD 2030 Platform.
WP2	Mapping of trends in food systems and related R&I policy frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of visions on the aspired European food systems and the corresponding FNS R&I system to ensure wider engagement with and ownership of the FOOD 2030 initiative • Evidence and strategic intelligence on trends, drivers and barriers in food systems and food systems research (R&I) in Europe (region and country level) and in addition from a global perspective to underline the urgency for future-proofing food systems science; • Mapping the governance of food policies and EU food systems R&I in a global context (i.e. set the scene for WP5) to identify strengths and weaknesses, policy needs, restrictions and requirements; • Mapping the performance and identify priorities of EU food systems in topics and impact towards delivering on FNS in Europe and SDGs. The results will directly feed into WP3&4, as well as WP5&6 and be part of the position paper in T4.3.
WP3	Identification of showcases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To map existing and past EU and international initiatives (or ‘cases’) to assess (1) what made specific cases outstanding in terms of (a) their impact with regard to the four FOOD 2030 priorities (nutrition, climate, circularity and innovation), (b) their organizational structure and involved processes, (c) their stakeholder engagement; and (2) how to transfer the knowledge of such examples to new initiatives; • To define cases as networks, research or innovation projects, demonstrations, open science initiatives, investments, or international collaborations that have contributed to food system R&I developments; • To develop guidelines that highlight components that were essential for the success of a broad range of cases, so that more R&I initiatives in the future can easily become showcases.
WP4	Exploration of roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify possible roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs that will increase the impact of the current initiatives operating in the field of FNS with the different stakeholders; • To identify the key barriers and key enablers, which have had or will have most impact on the implementation of these breakthroughs by the different stakeholders; • To foster the dialogue around the urgency, possible good practices and pathways for applications of the RRI concept to food system transformation; • To identify appropriate instruments for the identification of R&I breakthroughs that contribute to the multi-stakeholder, multi-level platform for the future/
WP5	Policy coherence and programme alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To establish Policy Labs within 10 countries which comprises of a network which mobilises stakeholders to align policies and organises and participates in RRI-based mutual learning and experimentation. • To create an EU Think Tank that supports the development of an

		<p>integrated vision for EU food systems to deliver impact on the societal challenge of FNS & a blue print for global collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop a guideline that supports the design and assessment of research programs and research calls/ applications with respect to their (potential) impact on FNS.
WP6	Building competences on food systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To establish 14 City Labs which design and deliver transformative hands-on future oriented trainings on food systems (R)R&I for Primary, Secondary and University level students and professionals. • To develop prototypes in order to produce a toolkit to roll out the activities and methodology in different settings.
WP7	Communication, dissemination and future engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To maximise the outreach and impact of FIT4FOOD2030's efforts, through (1) effective and targeted dissemination of project outputs, drawing on the networks and communication channels of the partners represented in the consortium, (2) targeted communication with multi-level stakeholders to support the mobilisation of a wide diversity of actors and the sustainability of the 'learning network'.
WP8	Learning for transformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor and evaluate the project in a way that it facilitates learning for transformation within the network and supports its development into a sustainable platform and its adherence to the principles of RRI.
WP9	Project management and coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure efficient execution of the project over the funding period in accordance with the European regulations, and realization of the project objectives, deliverables and milestones and at appropriate quality levels.
WP10	Ethics requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure compliance with project 'ethics requirements' set out in this WP.

Figure 1. Diagram showing the relationship of work packages of FIT4FOOD2030.

WP1 aims to develop and guide the overall methodology for the creation of the FOOD 2030 Platform – its structure and instruments.

WPs2-4 are similar in terms of content and tasks, being mapping exercises, though each with a different focus. WP2 will identify the general trends in food systems, related (R&I) policy frameworks

as well as drivers and barriers. WP3 will highlight specific showcases/best practices and develop recommendations for improvement of effectiveness of R&I measures. **WP4** will identify the roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs and key barriers & enablers which have had or will have the greatest impact on the implementation of these breakthroughs.

The actual network building and governance takes place in **WPs5 and 6**. In WP5 the EU Think Tank and Policy Labs are established, and dialogue and co-creation within and between different levels of the R&I policy landscape will be facilitated. WP6 entails the establishment of networks at city level and design and pilot testing of a set of needs-based, transformative, hands-on, future-oriented training to enhance competence building across a range of stakeholders.

Transformative learning in the Platform is fostered in **WP8**, where through close monitoring findings are discussed in reflection sessions. WP8 runs closely with WP1, both providing training and learning sessions needed for Policy Labs and City Labs.

WP9 is responsible for management and coordination.

All WPs will deliver to **WP7** which coordinates communication and dissemination of the results (outreach).

3. Partners and Organizational Structure

3.1 Partners

Partners of the FIT4FOOD2030 project are shown below.

Table 2. Partners of the FIT4FOOD2030 project.

No.	Partner Name	Partner Short Name	Country	Represented Network
1 (CO)	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	VU	Netherlands	
2	Oslo and Akershus University College of Applied Sciences	HiOA	Norway	
3	Austrian Institute of Technology	AIT	Austria	
4	Fundacio Privada Institut de Recerca de la Sida-Caixa	IRSiCaixa	Spain	
5	European Food Information Council	EUFIC	Belgium	
6	Association Européenne des Expositions Scientifiques, Techniques et Industrielles	Ecsite	Belgium	
7	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique	INRA	France	The Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (FACCE)
8	The Research Council Norway	RCN	Norway	JPI Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans (OCEANS)
9	The Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development	ZON	Netherlands	JPI A Healthy Diet for a Healthy Life (HDHL)
10	FoodDrinkEurope	F4L	Belgium	European Technology Platform (ETP) Food for Life
11	International Life Sciences	ILSI	Belgium	

	Institute European Branch			
12	Alma Mater Studiorum-University of Bologna	UniBO	Italy	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA)
13	Wageningen Research	WEcR	Netherlands	Metrics, Models and Foresight for European Sustainable Food And Nutrition Security (SUSFANS)
14	EIT Food	EIT FOOD	Belgium	FOOD Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC)
15	Municipality of Milan	CdM	Italy	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP)

The project additionally has the following organizations as (linked) Third Parties.

Table 3. Linked third parties to Ecsite

Third Party Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
Centre for Research and Analysis	CRA	Bulgaria
Science Centre AHHA Foundation	AHHA	Estonia
Ellinogermaniki Agogi	EH	Greece
Fondazione Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia Leonardo da Vinci	MUST	Italy
Environmental Social Sciences Research Group	ESSRG	Hungary

Table 4. Third parties that provide in-kind contributions against payment

Third Party Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
Environmental Social Sciences Research Group	ESSRG	Hungary

3.2 Policy Labs and City Labs

The Policy Labs and City Labs are shown in the tables below.

Table 5. Policy Labs

Country/region	Ministry/Department
Belgium /Flanders	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries
	Department of Economy, Science and Innovation
Hungary	Research Institute of Agricultural Economics
	Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture
Italy	Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry
	National Council for Agricultural Research and Economics
Lithuania	Ministry of Agriculture
	Food Institute of Kaunas University of Technology
Netherlands	Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality
	Ministry of Health, Wellbeing and Sport
Norway	Research Council Norway
Romania	Ministry of Research and Innovation
	National Institute of R&D for Food Bioresources

Table 6. City Labs

City	Institution
Sofia	Centre for Research and Analysis (CRA)
Tartu	AHHAA Foundation (AHHAA)
Athens	Ellinogermaniki Agogi (EA)
Budapest	Environmental Social Science Research Group (ESSRG)
Milan	Fondazione Museo Nazionale Della Scienza e Della Tecnologia Leonardo da Vinci (MUST)
Amsterdam	Amsterdam City Lab (VU)
Barcelona	Living Lab for Health (IrsiCaixa)

3.3 Overview of consortium bodies

General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) deals with partner enrolment and exit, budget changes, (intellectual property rights (IPR)) issues and conflicts.

Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board is the supervisor for the execution of the project. Moreover, it is responsible for proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GA.

External Advisory Boards (AB)

Two external Advisory Boards – the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and the Stakeholder Advisory Board (STAB) – give regular advice on relevant issues.

Coordinating Institute (CO)

The Coordinating Institute (CO) is responsible for efficient management of the project and individual activities with respect of time, budget and quality. It also functions as the intermediary for all communication between co-beneficiaries and the European Commission (EC). VU functions as the CO for the FIT4FOOD2030 project.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for developing detailed WP implementation plans on the basis of the current proposal, and for the efficient and effective implementation of these plans (see also Appendix 3 “Members of the Executive Board”).

The management structure of FIT4FOOD2030 is represented below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Management structure of FIT4FOOD2030.

3.4 General Assembly (GA)

The GA is ultimately **responsible** for the management of the project and consists of one representative from each partner in the consortium. The GA is chaired by the Project Coordinator (Coordinator). The GA shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions. In addition, all proposals made by the Executive Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the GA.

The following **decisions** shall be taken by the GA:

- Content, finance and IPR (e.g. advise and review the Project Results);
- Evolution of the consortium (e.g.: entry of a new partner, withdrawal of a partner);
- Appointments (the appointment, if necessary, of EB Members)

All decisions of the GA are taken with 2/3 majority votes, though the objective is unanimity. The quorum of the GA meetings is 2/3 of its members.

The GA will meet face-to-face, preceding and preparing the reporting obligations to the EC. At other times, communication between the GA members and the consortium will take place via e-mail, phone, or teleconference. See **Appendix 2** for members of the GA.

3.5 Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board (EB) consists of the Coordinator (chair) and the work package leaders. The EB is responsible for monitoring of the operational and financial progress of the project activities towards the main objectives of the project.

The EB is responsible for and has decision-making authority in:

- Preparing and organising of management meetings, including those of the GA;
- Consensus seeking among the Parties;
- Proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GA;
- Monitoring the effective and efficient implementation of the project;
- Collecting information at least every 6 months on the progress of the project, examining that information to assess the compliance of the project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, proposing modifications of the Consortium Plan to the GA.
- Supporting the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Funding Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables;
- Monitoring the overall course of the project, including major deviations in the course, objectives and/or financial budgets of the activities that require consulting the Funding Authority;
- Drafting the reports, upon consultation of the Parties if necessary, and associated documents and forms as required by EU GA;
- Preparing the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority;
- Appointing members of the Scientific Advisory Board and members of the Stakeholders Advisory Board (section 6.3.2.3.6);
- Informing and reporting to the GA of any major modifications in to the project-related work and/or deliverables together with proposing appropriate measures, as well as advising the GA in case of contingencies.

Furthermore, the EB acts as main body to facilitate interaction among the WPs in an efficient way.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the EB, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds (quorum).

See **Appendix 3** for list of members of the EB.

3.6 Stakeholder Advisory Board (STAB) and Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)

By means of two external advisory boards, FIT4FOOD2030 will seek regular advice on relevant issues.

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) will provide strategic expert advice on the scientific quality of the activities and deliverables, in order to overview that the Project will develop in accordance with the latest state-of-the-art in R&I for FNS. It will also advise on corrective measures in the content of the work if necessary and the dissemination and exploitation of the results.

The members of the SAB act as ethical advisors. More specifically, one member of the SAB will be an ethical advisor.

The Stakeholder Advisory Board (STAB) will provide advice on the quality of the activities and deliverables, in order to overview that the project will develop taking into account the different perspectives and interests of stakeholders. It will also advise on corrective measures in the content of the work and the dissemination and exploitation of the projects results.

See **Appendix 4** for members of the SAB and STAB, once the final lists are available. This list will also be uploaded on file sharing platform Edugroepen (see Chapter 7.1.2)

3.7 Coordinating Institute

The FIT4FOOD2030 project is coordinated by VU and acts as the intermediary between the partners and the European Commission (EC, Funding Authority).

In compliance with the EU GA and consistent with the CA, the coordinating institute (CO) – VU – is the intermediary for any communication with the EC and any partner. As such, the CO is responsible for:

- Acting as the primary spokesman on behalf of FIT4FOOD2030 for all formal written and verbal communication with the EC.
- Collecting, reviewing and submitting the obliged reports, technical input and associated documents and forms to the EC as required by the GA.
- Administering and distributing the financial contribution of the EC to the partners as agreed in the GA and CA.

3.8 Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and Task Leaders (TLs) are responsible for the detailed implementation of the WPs and tasks and preparation of the corresponding deliverables and milestones. The WPLs perform operative management at the level of their WP and are responsible for the following activities:

- Developing detailed WP implementation plans on the basis of the current proposal, and efficient and effective implementation of these plans;
- Reporting progress at project meetings and in management reports;
- Immediately reporting major decisions related to any deviation to the work plan;
- Coordinating the activities of the task leaders;
- Highlighting any partners whose contributions are of insufficient or of unacceptable quality.

TLs are responsible for management of the research within the task. The TLs assist the WPLs in planning, managing and performing their respective tasks in the WP context.

The Coordinator will support the WPLs in the implementation of all WPs stepping in to ensure the work plan is adhered to. The Coordinator will organize regular conference calls with WPLs, and – as necessary – partners involved in each WP. The WPLs report on progress at GA meetings.

4. Deliverables and Milestones

4.1 List of Deliverables & Milestones in chronological order

See **Appendix 5** for the lists of deliverables and milestones in chronological order.

4.2 Deliverable Review Procedure

Deliverables will be reviewed firstly by the WPL or an appointed team member of the specific WP for a first quality check, followed by two other WPLs with sufficient knowledge on the topic that needs to be reviewed. The EB will decide who reviews which deliverable. The deliverable is finally reviewed by the Coordinator. The review process and the timely completion of the review will be supervised by the project manager (VU). If major revisions are required, the deliverable will receive a second review by the first reviewer. To allow sufficient time for the reviewing process, a general timetable of the deliverable review procedure is shown below (table 7).

Table 7. General timetable of deliverable review procedure.

Action	Time allowance
Deliverable is sent to review	12 working days prior to submission to the EC
Reviewers return their feedback	3 working days after having received the deliverable
Deliverable is sent to review by the coordinator (and second review by reviewers if applicable)	4 working days after feedback from first review phase is received.
Coordinator and reviewers return their feedback	2 working days after having received the deliverable
Final submission to coordinator	1 working day after having received feedback by the coordinator (and second review if applicable)

See **Appendix 6** for the Deliverable Review Procedure in more detail. The Deliverable Review Procedure and schedules are uploaded to Edugroepen to be available to all partners.

5. Risk Management

Risk management entails identification, assessment, and follow-up of threats and opportunities likely to affect the project performance as a whole. Following a bottom-up approach, risks are identified in cooperation with all WP/task leaders and assessed using a simplified system of 3 variables (minor, moderate and high).

Essential characteristics of each risk (description, trigger event, owner, etc.) are defined. Actions addressed to affect probability and/or impact before the risk happens (mitigation plans) are defined for priority risks, and actions to be carried out if the risk happens (contingency plans) are devised as well.

A risk registry is initiated at the project preparation phase (see the EU GA, DoA, Part A, page 47). Currently, the CO is working on updating this with collaboration of EB members and the overall consortium to make it a comprehensive **risk registry** to be completed in M6. Yearly updates are planned.

6. Legal Aspects

6.1 Summary of clauses related to personal data

As described in article 1.2 of the CA of FIT4FOOD2030, there has been differentiated between three types of data:

- **Personal Data:** any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one of more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person.
- **Research Data:** retrospective and prospective clinical, pre-clinical, genetic, longitudinal, follow-up and other information (including but not limited to numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) about individuals, generated or made available pursuant to the Grant Agreement and/or this Consortium Agreement, and excluding Stakeholder Data.

- **Stakeholder Data:** information (including but not limited to numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) about individuals employed by or otherwise linked to a stakeholder and generated or made available by a party pursuant to the project.

As described in article 4.3 of the CA, in case of **Research Data**, it is only allowed to transfer pseudonymized data among partners of the consortium. Edugroepen can be used to transfer research data, including pseudonymized transcripts.

When personal data needs to be transferred, this needs to be processed in accordance with the article 4.2 of the CA:

“Each Party shall ensure that its work on the Project complies fully with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines which are effective during the duration of the Consortium Agreement, including those governing health and safety, data protection, including Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and its successor Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such personal data or its successor, and any implementation thereof in national law, and where relevant, the use of human subjects and good clinical practice (including national legislation implementing the Parliament’s Directive 2001/20/EC on good clinical practice and its successor Regulation 536/2014 (on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use).

In this regard, each Party shall maintain the confidentiality, in accordance with Article 10 of this Consortium Agreement, of all samples and Personal Data relating to the use of human subjects, which is created or used in the course of the Project. Each Party shall secure all necessary declarations or approvals from or to the relevant research ethics committees and authorities before undertaking any part of the Project requiring declaration or approval and shall, if required, obtain properly signed informed consent and acknowledgement forms from any human subjects or their legal guardians who they will involve in the Project.”

Furthermore, a **separate bilateral or multilateral data transfer agreement** specifying the conditions of transfer and processing of personal data by the recipient should be agreed on by the supplier and the recipient data, as described in article 4.3.

Further information on data management can be found at D9.1 Data Management Protocol.

6.2 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (EU GA) forms the legal basis for the implementation of the project. It consists of:

- Terms and Conditions (this is the core contract);
- Annex 1 Description of the action (DoA), consisting of Part A and Part B (DoA is a slightly modified version of the proposal);
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action, 2a. additional information on the estimated budget;
- Annex 3 Accession Forms for Beneficiaries;
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements;
- Annex 5 Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS);
- Annex 6 Model for the certificate on the methodology.

Although the core contract is signed between the EU and the Coordinator of the project, all partners have become individual contract partners with the commission by signing the Accession Forms. The EU GA must be kept by all partners and should be provided to the auditor in case of an audit. It is downloadable from the participant portal; in the document library of the FIT4FOOD2030 project, as well as the “Documents” folder in Edugroepen page.

6.3 Consortium Agreement

Whereas the EU GA is signed between the EU and the partners, the Consortium Agreement (CA) is signed between the partners themselves. It arranges in more detail the provisions of the EU GA, such as, but not limited to: financial issues, payments, management, decision making, conflict resolution, intellectual property rights and liability. The Consortium Agreement must also be kept by the partners and must be shown in case of audits. (available under the folder “Documents” in the Edugroepen page).

6.4 Amendments

During the project, circumstances may arise to call for a request to the EU for an amendment of the Grant Agreement. Reasons may vary, but could be:

- Change of partner(s);
- Change of legal entity;
- Changes in the Budget (*EU GA: Annex 2*);
- Changes in the DoA (*EU GA: Annex 1*).

In case an amendment is needed, the Coordinator shall submit such a request after an autonomous decision by all partners in the General Assembly. After approval the Coordinator shall distribute the revised Grant Agreement to the partners, replacing former versions.

Budget changes that do not affect the content of DoA can be taken care by the consortium itself; decision through the General Assembly and inform the EC Project Officer (EC PO). Amendments may be requested by any of the project partners.

7. Communication

7.1 Internal Communication

Internal communication is considered the communication within the consortium.

E-mail

Many people may be working on a number of different projects and are likely to receive numerous emails every day, therefore, a standard subject title is proposed. This helps to quickly recognise the project related emails.

Project related e-mails should include in the subject title: ‘FIT4FOOD2030’ and WP number (if applicable) followed by a more specific description of the subject, deadline for feedback or reply, see below an example:

[Subject: ‘FIT4FOOD2030’ EB meeting minutes, till January 10 2018]

If the email requires an action by the recipients, the subject line can also include a phrase ‘Action needed’.

Furthermore, it is required to copy the Coordinator (Jacqueline Broerse, j.e.w.broerse@vu.nl) and in most important e-mail communications. In critical cases, EC PO may also be included in the CC. There are different mailing lists, which can be found on Edugroepen together with the contact list. These are namely: general mailing list (all people involved), EB (WP leaders) and GA (one person in charge of representing the partner at the GA). Required changes can be sent to the Project Manager: Dr. Tomris Cesuroglu (t.cesuroglu@vu.nl) and/or the Project Management support team: Alanya den Boer (a.c.l.den.boer@vu.nl) and Amy Berkhout (a.berkhout@vu.nl).

Internal communication platform

Edugroepen will act as repository for working documents, minutes and reports. Edugroepen is based on Microsoft Sharepoint 2016. The address of Edugroepen is: <https://www.edugroepen.nl>.

Every member of the consortium has access to Edugroepen. Every member receives an invitation by email to create an account on Edugroepen. A large number of institutions is connected to Edugroepen. If an institution is not connected to Edugroepen, it is possible to create a password. In case of problems/need for a new account, please contact Alanya den Boer (a.c.l.den.boer@vu.nl).

There are three different permission levels, referring to “visitors”, “members”, and “owners”. All people from the consortium who are active within one or more work packages will be invited as a member. Members can use Edugroepen to read, download, edit and upload (final) documents.

There are specific Edugroepen subpages for Policy Lab and City Lab coordinators, as well as for the expert panel of WP3. The members of these groups don’t have access to the rest of the consortium’s pages and documents.

Document Titles

All document titles need to conform the standards provided in table 8 below.

Table 8. Standards document titles.

	Deliverables	Meetings	Conferences
First letters	FIT4FOOD2030	FIT4FOOD2030	FIT4FOOD2030
Next letters	–	–	–
Underscore	Deliverable number [Dx.y] [x=WP number, y=deliverable]	Type of document (i.e. Agenda, Minutes, Presentation). In case of presentation, include WP.	Event title
Next letters	Short explanatory title for the document.	Date and location of the meeting	Date and location of the meeting
Underscore	–	–	–
Next letters (for presentations only)		Short name of organisation and initials of presenter.	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter.
Underscore		–	–
Next letters	“v” and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1 = draft version, v1.0 = final version, v1.1 = revised version after final version]	“v” and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1 = draft version, v1.0 = final version, v1.1 = revised version after final version].	“v” and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1 = draft version, v1.0 = final version, v1.1 = revised version after final version].

Deliverable documents: [....._Dx.y_Title_v.....]

Example: FIT4FOOD2030_D1.1_Project Execution Handbook_v0.1]

Meeting documents: [....._Type of document_Date and Location, Organisation, Initials_v.....]

Example: [FIT4FOOD2030_Executive Board meeting Agenda 12 Dec 17_171204_v.0.2]

Conference documents: [....._Event title_Date and Location, Organisation, Initials_v.....]

Example: [FIT4FOOD2030_Prekickoff_171017_VU, B.J. Regeer_v1.0]

7.2 External Communication

External communication is considered towards parties outside the consortium, target groups of the project, stakeholders and the EC PO. The external communication is part of WP7 (Communication, dissemination and future engagement). Communication of project results is an important part of a H2020 project.

Project website and hashtag

The project website is set up for external communication purposes. It can be found at <http://www.fit4food2030.eu/>. The project website is created with information about the project, its objectives, activities, results, partners, news and events.

At the time of the last update of this PEH, a temporary web site is in place. By the end of M6, a web site with full functionality will be introduced.

For Twitter communications, the project will use the #FOOD2030EU, which is EU's hashtag for FOOD 2030.

General Requirements

You are requested to indicate at all times that the project has received funding from the EU, using the following:

- Display the **EU emblem** (when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence):

- Include the following text (**Disclaimer**):

'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774088'.

'The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and reflects in no way the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.'

You can find the logo on the Edugroepen page. It is recommended to always place the project logo on the front page of the document and the EU logo at the left side of the footer of the first page in the document.

Document standard/Templates

All public documentation needs to conform the document standards provided by the CO. The document standard could be used for:

- Official EU reports (such as Periodic, Final);
- Public documents by the consortium;
- Project deliverables (in a report format);
- And any documents that are declared as public by the consortium.

The preview of a template for a document standard can be found in **Appendix 7**, as well as on Edugroepen (folder "Documents > Templates").

For internal project documents, it is also advised to apply this standard, such as WP meeting agenda and minutes.

Specific Project Presentation standard/Template

On Edugroepen you will find the standard Fit4FOOD2030 PowerPoint presentation once it is finished by WP7. This template can be used in external communications.

8. Meetings and Reporting

8.1 Meetings

Details of meetings of the different bodies are shown in table 9 below.

Table 9. Meetings

Body	Frequency	Preparation	Method
General Assembly	Every 12 months: M3, M11, M23, M35	EB	Face-to-face (combined with annual consortium meeting). * Extraordinary meetings can be convened at any time, following a written request by (or via) the EB.
Executive Board	Every 3 months	EB	EB meetings that will be held through teleconference (3 times a year), and face-to-face (directly preceding the annual GA). Extraordinary meetings can be convened at any time upon written request of any Member of the EB.
Advisory Board	On regular basis: SAB: at least once a year STAB: at least twice a year	EB	SAB and STAB meetings can be face-to-face (combined with annual consortium meetings) or teleconference. Regular contact by e-mail. Additional ad hoc teleconference when needed.
WP teams (WPLs and other key investigators participating in the WP)	Monthly	WPLs	Face-to-face or teleconference. Ad hoc teleconference when needed.
All members of the consortium (2-day annual consortium meeting)	Every 12 months: M11, M23, M35	EB	Face-to-face.

*As described in section 6.2.2.8 of the CA, any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the Coordinator circulates to all members of the Consortium a written document (by e-mail), which is then agreed by the defined majority of all members of the Consortium.

The annual consortium meetings will take place in Brussels and will be prepared by one of the Brussels-based partners together with the CO (WP9).

For every meeting taken place, **minutes** should be sent to the Coordinator. The minutes of the meetings may be submitted to the EU Project Officer, if required.

Costs for travel and accommodation to participate in these meetings have to be covered by each partners' own budget. (exceptions may apply, depending on the decisions of WPs)

8.2 Reporting

Throughout the lifetime of the project there are:

- Two periodic report(s) to the EU (financial & technical progress);
- A final report.

8.3 Reporting Calendar

Table 10. Reporting Calendar

Kind of report	Period covered	Template ready by and uploaded to Edugroepen by CO	Deadline to send to Coordinator	By whom?	Finalised & submitted to EC by CO
Periodic report 1	M1-M18	M18 – April 2019	M19 – May 2019	WPL	M20 – June 2019
Periodic report 2	M19-M36	M36 – October 2020	M37 – November 2020	WPL	M38 – December 2020
Final report	M1-M36	n/a	n/a	CO	M38 – January 2021

8.4 Periodic Reports

The periodic report (EU GA: Article 20.3) must be submitted by the EC within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. This report must include explanations for any deviations (budget and content) from the DoA (EU GA: Annex 1). The periodic report consists of a technical report and a financial report.

The **'periodic technical report'** consists of two parts; Part A and Part B:

Part A is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal (e.g. the deliverables). The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the life of the project. Part A contains:

- The cover page;
- A summary which can be used for publications by the EC, and;
- The answers to the questionnaire (covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact).

The Coordinator is responsible for part A.

Part B is the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

WPLs compile a report on their WP together with their TLs (Part B) and send it to the CO one month before the deadline for uploading it in the participant portal. The CO consolidates the provided information and sends the complete periodic technical report to the consortium for review. The final approved version will be uploaded in to the Participant Portal by the CO.

Each partner provides an overview of the resources they used within the given period, including person months spent and an overview of the other direct costs. Explanations need to be made in case there are deviations from planned use of resources in Annex 1, including the person-months.

The Periodic Report Template can be found on the EC website under H2020 reference documents: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tmpl-periodic-rep_en.pdf

The **'periodic financial report'** consists of:

- An individual financial statement (*EU GA: Annex 4*) for each partner, for the reporting period concerned. This financial statement must detail the eligible costs for each budget category. Each partner *and linked third parties* must declare all eligible costs, even if costs exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget.
- An explanation of the use of resources and information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each partner for the reporting period concerned;
- A 'periodic summary financial statement' will be created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements of the partners, including the request for interim payment.

The Financial Signatories (F-signs; persons who are authorised, on behalf of their organisation, to sign financial statements in H2020 projects) of each partner will be able to complete online their own Financial Statement including the explanations on the use of resources, (also for their third parties) (also see *section 8.5.2*). The Coordinator will have a final check on the statements and the CO will electronically submit to the EC.

8.5 Final Reports

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the CO must submit the final report **within 60 calendar days** following the end of the last reporting period. The Final Report Template is available at EC website under H2020 reference documents:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/funding/reference_docs.html

The **final report** must include the following:

A **'final technical report'** containing:

- A **summary** for publication containing: an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
- The conclusions on the action and;

- The socio-economic impact of the action.

The Coordinator compiles this final technical report in consultation with the partners.

A **'final financial report'** containing:

- A **'final summary financial statement'**, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements of the partners for all reporting periods;
- A **'certificate on the financial statements'** for each partner (and for each linked third party), if it requests a total contribution of EUR 325 000 (or more) reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs.

8.6 Financial Reporting in Detail

8.6.1 Budget

The budget contains the estimated eligible costs, broken down by Partner (and linked third parties) and budget category (*EU GA: Articles 5, 6, and 14*).

The budget is based on estimated costs and person months. Frequent internal reporting assures that these budgets are monitored well and that under- and over spending is noticed at an early stage. Please note that in reporting, actual costs must be reported and not budgeted ones. The budget, as presented in the EU GA is available on Edugroepen, and in **Appendix 8**. Indicative budget breakdown for other direct costs for each WP is provided by the CO and can be found in Edugroepen.

The budget categories are listed in the EU GA: Article 6.2, these are:

Direct personnel costs:

- Costs for employees (or equivalent);
- Costs for natural persons working under a direct contract;
- Costs of personnel seconded by a third party against payment;
- Costs for SME owners without salary;
- Costs for beneficiaries that are natural persons without salary.

Direct costs of subcontracting

If necessary to implement the action, the partner may award subcontracts covering the implementation of certain action tasks described in the EU GA. The partner must award the subcontracts ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price. In doing so, it must avoid any conflict of interests (*EU GA: Article 35*).

Other direct costs:

- Travel costs and related subsistence allowances;
- Costs of equipment, infrastructure, or other assets;
- Costs of other goods and services;
- Capitalised and operating costs of large research infrastructure.

Costs of in-kind contributions not used on partner's premises.

Indirect costs:

Indirect costs should be calculated like as: $0,25 \times (\text{direct personnel costs (A)} + \text{other direct costs (B)} - \text{Costs of in kind contributions not used on the partner's premises (E)})$. Note that costs of subcontracting are excluded from this 25% flat-rate.

8.6.2 Individual Financial Statement – Declaration of Eligible Costs

The individual financial statement needs to be submitted electronically by each partner to the EU through the Participant Portal (*EU GA: Annex 4*).

To be able to login to the Participant Portal you need to have an ECAS (European Commission Authentication Service) password. The procedure below will be updated, once the process is available in the EU Participant portal.

Procedure:

1. Go to the sign-up page and create your ECAS account. Make sure you selected the right domain: External
2. Choose the tab 'my Projects'. If FIT4FOOD2030 is not listed, contact the CO.
3. Click in the column 'Actions' on 'PR' (= Periodic Reporting).
4. Click under your organisation on the 'Financial statement'. Fill in the requested information with explanations.
5. Once everything is filled in press "save".
6. Then click on the button "inform F-sign", the F-sign will be asked by e-mail to sign the financial statement electronically. If an organisation has not yet added a F-sign to the project (the PF-sign), the LEAR needs to be contacted. The LEAR needs to nominate a F-sign for the organisation and then the participant contact needs to add the F-sign to the project.
7. The PF-sign then needs to submit the financial statement to the Coordinator.
8. The Coordinator will make a final check and then submit the financial statements including all reports to the EU through the Participant Portal.

8.5.3. Audit – Certificate on the Financial Statements

A Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS) is requested for each partner in case of total contribution of EUR 325 000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs, calculated on the basis of its actual cost accounting practices. This means excluding the reimbursement of indirect costs (25%).

Partners submit:

- Either one certificate per reporting period. Note: choose this option, only when you expect to exceed the threshold of EUR 325.000 at the end of the project;
- Or a single CFS for the whole project. In both cases, the certificate and related costs may only be submitted with the final financial report.

Please note that you have to keep the financial records of the expenses in this project, for a minimum of **5 years** after the final payment has been received – digital or hardcopy.

The **template** is available in *EU GA Annex 5* and on the EC website under [H2020 Reference Documents](#) (go to 'Templates and Forms' > 'Project reporting templates' > 'Annex 5 – Template for the Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS)').

8.5.4. Keeping records- supporting documentation

Each partner must — for a period of five years after the payment of the balance keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the declared costs to be eligible. The documents need to be the original documents. Digital and digitalised documents are accepted if national law accepts these documents as originals.

The partners must keep the records and documentation according to their usual cost accounting practices and internal control procedures. There must be a track between the amounts declared, the amounts recorded in accounts and the amounts stated in the supporting documentation (audit trail).

For the different cost categories, consider the following documents:

Direct personnel costs:

- Monthly signed time sheets (8.5.5. Time recording);
- Calculation of hourly rate (EU GA: Article 6.2);
- Proof of paid salary;
- Labour contracts.

Other direct costs (travel costs and related subsistence allowances, equipment costs, costs of other goods and services):

- Quotations (sub)contracts;
- All receipts of expenditure;
- Meeting documents: signed presence lists, minutes, agenda;
- Calculations of depreciation costs charged to the project.

Direct costs of subcontracting:

- Quotations (sub)contracts;
- Signed (sub)contracts.

8.5.5. Time Recording

For personnel costs (declared as actual costs or on the basis of unit costs), the partners must keep time records for the number of hours declared. The time records must be in writing and approved by the persons working on the action and their supervisors, at least monthly (EU GA article 18.1).

The time recording can be done by using a timesheet on paper or in a computer-based system. A template for time-sheets is available on the Participant Portal:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/89556/financial_guidelines_en.pdf

This template is not mandatory; beneficiaries may use their own model, provided that it fulfils the minimum conditions and it contains at least the information detailed below.

Time records should include:

- Title and number of the project, as specified in the EU GA;
- Partners full name, as specified in the EU GA;
- Full name, date and signature of the person working for the project;
- Number of hours worked for the action in the period covered by the time record; for reasons of assurance and legal certainty it is highly recommended that the number of hours

is detailed per day (hours worked for the action in each day);

- Supervisor's full name and signature;
- Reference to the WP described in the DoA (EU GA: *Annex 1*), to easily verify that the work carried out matches the work assigned and the person-months reported to the action.

Information included in timesheets must match records of annual and sick leave taken, and work-related travel.

8.5.6. Budget Transfers

With the consent of the Project EB a re-distribution of person-months between partners may be considered. This re-distribution is allowed without requesting an amendment (*EU GA: Article 55*) provided that it does not imply a substantial change to the action as described in the EU GA. All other re-allocations of budget items need to be discussed in order to decide whether to apply for an amendment to the EU GA.

The maximum grant amount (*EU GA: Article 5*) can however **NEVER be increased.**

8.5.7. Payments

The following types of payments are foreseen:

Pre-financing at the start of the project: 3.199,999.00 (three million one hundred and ninety nine thousand nine hundred and ninety nine EURO).

Pre-financing funds remain EU property until they are 'cleared' against eligible costs accepted by the European Commission.

Interim payment following the approval of the periodic reports:

After approval of the formal periodic reports an interim payment will be issued.

After the first periodic report:

- November 2017 (M1) – April 2019 (M18): expected amount: 399.999,88 (three hundred ninety nine thousand nine hundred and ninety nine EURO and eighty eight cents).

Final payment following the approval of the final report:

The final payment will be transferred after the approval of the final report and consists of the difference between the calculated EU contribution (on the basis of the eligible costs) minus the amounts already paid.

9. Dissemination of Results and Open Access

The partners must - as soon as possible (but not before a decision on their possible protection) — disseminate their results (i.e. make them public). Some of the classic forms of dissemination are:

- Website;
- Peer reviewed publication (open access);
- Presentation at a scientific conference.

The dissemination measures should however be consistent with the ‘Communication and Dissemination Plan’ (WP7) and proportionate to the impact expected from the action. Deliverable 7.1 ‘Communication and Dissemination Plan’ will be ready in M3. This document provides with more guidelines. When deciding on dissemination, the partners must also consider the other partners’ legitimate interests.

9.1 Open Access

9.1.1 Open Access to Scientific Publications

Each partner must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

- As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.
Moreover, the partner must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest: on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- Ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following: the terms ‘European Union (EU)’ and ‘Horizon 2020’; the name of the action, acronym and grant number; the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and a persistent identifier.

9.1.2 Open Access to Research Data

The FIT4FOOD2030 project participates in the open access to research data pilot (ORDP), described in article 29.3 of the model Grant Agreement (GA). This means all research data will be made openly available. Data needs to be stored and archived in public and open repositories to ensure access by third parties.

Data generated within FIT4FOOD2030 will be archived in **Zenodo**, which is an open and public research data repository funded by the European Commission (via the OpenAire Projects FP7 and Horizon 2020), CERN and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation¹. Besides, consortium partners might use open institution-based repositories.

Deliverable 9.1 Data Management Protocol (DMP) describes the above in more detail.

9.1.3 Dissemination Rules

The complete rules for dissemination are covered in Section 8.3, 8.4 and 8.5 of the CA and Article 29 of the EU GA.

More concrete, the partner wishing to publish, present or disclose information about the project must follow the following procedure:

¹ <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

Send an email at least **45 calendar days** before publication/disclosure of information to the whole consortium. Provide the foreseen title, list of contributing authors, abstract of the content and the purpose of the publication. Any objections to the planned publication can be made within **30 calendar days** after receipt of the notice; if no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

An objection is justified if:

- the projection of the objecting party's results or background is adversely affected.
- the objecting party's legitimate academic or commercial interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed;
- the publication contains Confidential Information of the objecting Party.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. The objecting partner can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that confidential information has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting partner. A partner shall not include in any dissemination activity another partner's results or background without obtaining written approval, unless they are already published. The author informs the Coordinator when the planned publication has been accepted for publishing (for monitoring proposes).

Appendix 1. Abbreviations and Acronyms

AB	Advisory Board
AGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
CO	Coordinating Institute (VU)
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CoP	Community of Practice
DoA	Description of the action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECAS	European Commission Authentication Service
EU	The European Union
EU GA	EU Grant Agreement
FNS	Food and Nutrition Security
GA	General Assembly
OA	Open Access
OSc	Open Science
PEH	Project Execution Handbook
EC PO	Project Officer from the European Commission
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
STAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Appendix 2. Members of the General Assembly

No.	Partner Name	Name	E-mail
1 (CO)	VU	Jacqueline Broerse	j.e.w.broerse@vu.nl
2	HiOA	Helge Svare	Helge.Svare@afi.hioa.no
3	AIT	Beatrix Wepner	beatrix.wepner@ait.ac.at
4	IrsiCaixa	Rosina Malagrida	rmalagrida@irsicaixa.es
5	EUFIC	Raymond Gemen	raymond.gemen@eufic.org
6	Ecsite	Carmen Fenollosa	cfenollosa@ecsitem.eu
7	INRA	Heather Mckhann	heather.mckhann@inra.fr
8	RCN	Thomas Redd	tre@forskingsradet.no
9	ZON	Jolien Wenink	Wenink@zonmw.nl
10	F4L	Rebeca Fernández Jochen Weiss (ETP)	r.fernandez@fooddrinkeurope.eu j.weiss@uni-hohenheim.de
11	ILSI -Europe	Bettina Schelkle	bschelkle@ilsieurope.be
12	UniBo	Francesco Capozzi	francesco.capozzi@unibo.it
13	WEcR	Thom Achterbosch	thom.achterbosch@wur.nl
14	EIT Food	Francesca Mancini	francesca.mancini@eitfood.eu
15	CdM	Chiara Minotti Andrea Magarini	chiara.minotti@comune.milano.it Andrea.Magarini@comune.milano.it

Appendix 3. Members of the Executive Board

WP	WP Title	Name(s) Work Package Leader(s)	E-mail
WP1	Methodology to build the FOOD2030 Platform	Barbara Regeer (VU)	b.j.regeer@vu.nl
WP2	Mapping of trends in food systems and related R&I policy frameworks	Beatrix Wepner (AIT)	beatrix.wepner@ait.ac.at
WP3	Identification of showcases	Bettina Schelkle (ILSI Europe)	bschelkle@ilsieurope.be
		Francesca Mancini (EIT Food)	francesca.mancini@eitfood.eu
WP4	Exploration of roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs	Rebeca Fernández (F4L) Jochen Weiss	r.fernandez@fooddrinkeurope.eu j.weiss@uni-hohenheim.de
WP5	Policy coherence and programme alignment	Jolien Wenink (ZON)	Wenink@zonmw.nl
WP6	Building competences on food systems	Carmen Fenollosa (Ecsite)	cfenollosa@ecsitem.eu
WP7	Communication, dissemination and future engagement	Raymond Gemen (EUFIC)	raymond.gemen@eufic.org
WP8	Learning for transformation	Helge Svare (HiOA)	Helge.Svare@afi.hioa.no
WP9	Project management and coordination	Jacqueline Broerse (VU, Coordinator) Tomris Cesuroglu (VU, Project Manager)	j.e.w.broerse@vu.nl t.cesuroglu@vu.nl

Appendix 4. Members of the Advisory Boards

Members of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and the Stakeholder Advisory Board (STAB) will be included, once the final lists are available.

Appendix 5. List of Deliverables and Milestones in Chronological Order

List of Deliverables (Bold indicates a change of the original date mentioned in the DoA.)

Nr.	Title	WP	Lead Beneficiary	Month
D1.1	Tools and training guideline for setting up and guiding CoPs	WP1	1-VU	4
D1.2	Database of contacts with relevant stakeholders	WP1	2-HiOA	4
D1.5	Process architecture for mutual exchange between CoPs within the FOOD 2030 Platform	WP1	1-VU	4
D7.1	Communication and dissemination plan	WP7	5-EUFIC	4
D8.1	Tool and training guide Dynamic Learning Agenda	WP8	2-HiOA	4
D5.2	Terms of Reference of EU Think Tank	WP5	1-VU	6
D7.3	Project identity and Website	WP7	5-EUFIC	6
D9.1	Data management Protocols	WP9	1-VU	6
D9.2	Project Execution Handbook	WP9	1-VU	6
D2.1	Report on baseline and description of identified trends, drivers and barriers of the food system and R&I	WP2	3-AIT	9
D3.1	Report on detailed data set of 100-150 (R)R&I cases	WP3	11-ILSI	10
D1.3	Tools and training guideline for identifying showcases and designing roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs	WP1	1-VU	11 (part goes to M7)
D2.2	Report on overview of needs, barriers and enablers for policies and governance of EU food systems and FNS R&I - comparison to global food systems	WP2	12-UniBo	12
D2.3	Résumé of performance of EU food systems towards European FNS and SDGs	WP2	13-WEcR	12
D4.1	Report on inventory of R&I breakthroughs	WP4	10-F4L	12
D10.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP10	1-VU	12
D10.2	POPD – Requirement No. 2	WP10	1-VU	12
D6.1	Catalogue on analysis of contents and formats for, and needs on trainings	WP6	6-Ecsite	13
D4.2	Report on key success factors for realisation of breakthroughs	WP4	3-AIT	16
D4.3	Position paper on urgency, good practices and pathways for applications of the RRI concept to food system transformation	WP4	13-WEcR	16
D1.4	Tools and training guideline for guiding lab activities	WP1	1-VU	16
D3.2	Report on selected showcases, including criteria for assessment of R&I cases, and ranking	WP3	11-ILSI	16
D3.3	Catalogue of identified showcases (criteria + impacts)	WP3	14-EIT Food	24
D6.2	Report on piloting of educational modules	WP6	6-Ecsite	24
D7.2	Stakeholder engagement plan	WP7	5-EUFIC	24
D6.3	Toolkit for use of educational modules	WP6	6-Ecsite	26

D5.4	International Collaboration	WP5	9-ZON	30
D3.4	Impact assessment and policy guidance tool	WP3	14-EIT Food	32
D4.4	Report on instruments for the identification of R&I breakthroughs for the future	WP4	10-F4L	32
D5.3	Guidelines/framework for designing and assessing applications towards impact on FNS	WP5	7-INRA	32
D5.5	Practical guide or handbook to support set up (of activities for) a Policy Lab	WP5	9-ZON	32
D8.2	Report on tasks 8.1-8.5	WP8	2-HiOA	32
D5.1	Position Paper on lessons learned to adjust D4.3	WP5	9-ZON	34
D8.3	Toolbox for integrated reflexive M&E in R&I development	WP8	2-HiOA	35
D1.6	Updated and final version of all instruments and tools	WP1	1-VU	36
D7.4	Project leaflet and other Materials	WP7	5-EUFIC	36
D7.5	Plan for continued communication with stakeholders	WP7	5-EUFIC	36
D9.3	Final report on ethical Issues	WP9	1-VU	36
D9.4	Report of external Evaluator	WP9	1-VU	36

List of Milestones (Bold indicates a change of the original date mentioned in the DoA.)

Nr.	Title	WP	Lead Beneficiary	Month
MS1	Establishment working group for project identity	WP7	5-EUFIC	1
MS2	Establishment of the Think Tank	WP5	9-ZON	3
MS3	Establishment of Policy Labs	WP5	9-ZON	3
MS4	Establishment of City Labs	WP6	6-Ecsite	3
MS8	Kick-off meeting	WP9	1-VU	3
MS5	Development of process to ensure dissemination by all partners	WP7	5-EUFIC	4
MS6	Training session for CoP coordinators #1: setting up CoPs, activities phase 1	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	1-VU	4
MS7	Training of CoP coordinators in using the Dynamic Learning Agenda	WP8	2-HiOA	4
MS9	Meeting to identify criteria on how to identify showcases	WP3	11-ILSI	6
MS10	Maps on visions, trends, drivers, barriers, food policies and governance of EU food systems and related R&I and EU food systems performance completed	WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6	3-AIT	10
MS11	Workshops on the identification of potential R&I breakthroughs	WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6	3-AIT	10
MS14	1st annual conference	WP9	1-VU	12

MS12	Training & learning session #2: on designing and prioritising pathways to R&I breakthroughs, integrating showcase analysis	WP1, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	1-VU	13 (City Labs M7 and Policy Labs M13)
MS13	Learning workshop for lab coordinators #1	WP8	2-HiOA	13 (City labs M7 and Policy labs M13)
MS15	Workshops on the prioritisation of potential R&I breakthroughs and identification of barriers and incentives	WP4, WP5, WP6	10-F4L	14
MS16	Workshop to rank and select showcases	WP3	11-ILSI	15
MS17	Training session #3: guiding lab activities	WP1	1-VU	16
MS18	Learning workshop for lab coordinators #2	WP8	2-HiOA	16 (City labs M13 and Policy Labs M16)
MS19	Workshop for discussion of position paper	WP4	10-F4L	16
MS20	Commitment of follower countries/ regions for Policy Labs	WP5	9-ZON	16
MS21	Piloting of educational training prototypes	WP6	6-Ecsite	17
MS22	Training session #4: experiment-to-experiment learning and training of followers	WP1	1-VU	24
MS23	Learning workshop for lab coordinators #3	WP8	2-HiOA	24
MS24	2nd annual conference	WP9	1-VU	24
MS25	Reflexive workshop for all participants	WP8	2-HiOA	24
MS26	Launch of the Toolkit for training	WP6	6-Ecsite	26
MS27	Targeted consultation of the draft set of recommendations	WP4	10-F4L	28
MS28	High level debates	WP7	5-EUFIC	32
MS29	Scientific sessions	WP7	5-EUFIC	32
MS30	Piloting of impact assessment and policy guidance tool completed	WP3	11-ILSI	32
MS31	Final learning workshop	WP1, WP8	2-HiOA	35
MS32	Final conference	WP7	5-EUFIC	35

Appendix 6. Deliverable Review Procedure

Deliverable Review Procedure

This document describes the deliverable review procedure for the FIT4FOOD2030 project. Deliverables will be reviewed firstly by the work package leader for a first quality check, followed by two other work package leaders with sufficient knowledge on the topic that needs to be reviewed. The work package leader may delegate this task to a team member from that work package, provided that this person has sufficient knowledge on the topic.

The Executive Board will decide who reviews which deliverable. The deliverable is finally reviewed by the Coordinator. The review process and the timely completion of the review will be supervised by the project manager. The Coordinator and the project manager will propose the Executive Board a scheme for the review process, including who reviews which deliverable and a timeline.

Deliverables are expected to be delivered 10 working days ahead of the deadline described in the grant agreement, allowing sufficient time for the reviewing process. After submission, reviewers have three working days to submit the results of their review. The submitter then has two days to revise the deliverable and send it to the coordinator. If major revisions are required (see criteria below) the deliverable will receive a second review by the first reviewer. The coordinator (and reviewers if applicable) have two days to provide additional feedback which provides the submitter one day for final revisions. This process is outlined in table 1.

Table 1. Deliverable review procedure

Action	Time allowance
Deliverable is sent to review	12 working days prior to submission to the EC
Reviewers return their feedback	3 working days after having received the deliverable
Deliverable is sent to review by the coordinator (and second review by reviewers if applicable)	4 working days after feedback from first review phase is received.
Coordinator and reviewers return their feedback	2 working days after having received the deliverable
Final submission to coordinator	1 working day after having received feedback by the coordinator (and second review if applicable)

Reviewing Schedule

Deliverable No.	
Deliverable Name	
Organization responsible for the deliverable	
Deliverable author	
Work Package No.	
Reviewing Schedule	Date Planned Date received Date reviewed
Work Packager leader	
Reviewer 1	
Reviewer 2	
Coordinator	

Deliverable Internal Review Form

Reviewer			
Primary review method (mark X)	Track changes (directly into deliverable) <input type="checkbox"/>		Comment sheet (below) <input type="checkbox"/>
Review Summary			
Please rate the deliverable on the points below using the following criteria: RED: Major revisions required before the deliverable is at acceptable standard. AMBER: Some revisions required before the deliverable is at acceptable standard. GREEN: Deliverable is at acceptable standard and/or minor revisions are required.			
Description	Rating	Additional comments	
Relevance of the deliverable <i>Does the deliverable address the project objectives described in the Description of Work?</i>	AMBER		
Technical quality <i>Is the methodology/ argumentation sound? Are the claims backed up?</i>	RED		
Presentation <i>Is the deliverable well-written and readable? Is it organized well?</i>	RED		
Overall rating	RED		

If you have not added comments directly to the deliverable document please detail required revisions below:

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FIT4FOOD2030

Towards FOOD 2030 - Future-proofing the European food systems through research & innovation

Appendix 7. Template for a Document Standard

Title

Subtitle (heading 2)

Subtitle 2 (heading 3)

Body text

- Bullet list
- Bullet list
- Bullet list

Subtitle (heading 2)

Subtitle 2 (heading 3)

Body text

- Bullet list
- Bullet list
- Bullet list

Table 1. Table captions have font size 10

Appendix 8. Budget

Participants Budget

No	Participant	Country	(A) Direct personnel costs/€	(B) Other direct costs/€	(C) Direct costs of subcontracting/€	(D) Direct costs of providing financial support to third parties/€	(E) Costs of inkind contributions not used on the beneficiary's premises/€	(F) Indirect Costs/ € (=0.25(A+B-E))	(G) Special unit costs covering direct & indirect costs/€	(H) Total estimated eligible costs/€ (=A+B+C+D+F+G)	(I) Reimbursement rate (%)	(J) Max. EU Contribution/€ (=H*I)	(K) Requested EU Contribution/€
1	VUA	NL	422.500,00	125.725,00	20.000,00			137.056,25		705.281,25	1,00	705.281,25	705.281,25
2	HiOA	NO	193.250,00	17.000,00				52.562,50		262.812,50	1,00	262.812,50	262.812,50
3	AIT	AT	269.700,00	72.000,00				85.425,00		427.125,00	1,00	427.125,00	427.125,00
4	IrsiCaixa	ES	159.250,00	43.124,00				50.593,50		252.967,50	1,00	252.967,50	252.967,50
5	EUFIC	BE	159.000,00	62.500,00				55.375,00		276.875,00	1,00	276.875,00	276.875,00
6	Ecsite	BE	175.432,00	26.500,00				50.483,00		252.415,00	1,00	252.415,00	252.415,00
-	CRA	BG	10.028,00	13.000,00				5.757,00		28.785,00	1,00	28.785,00	28.785,00
-	AHHAA	EST	8.740,00	13.000,00				5.435,00		27.175,00	1,00	27.175,00	27.175,00
-	EA	GR	35.000,00	13.000,00				12.000,00		60.000,00	1,00	60.000,00	60.000,00
-	MUST	IT	35.000,00	13.000,00				12.000,00		60.000,00	1,00	60.000,00	60.000,00
7	INRA	FR	116.000,00	8.000,00				31.000,00		155.000,00	1,00	155.000,00	155.000,00
8	RCN	NO	60.750,00	5.500,00				16.562,50		82.812,50	1,00	82.812,50	82.812,50
9	ZON	NL	192.000,00	185.000,00				94.250,00		471.250,00	1,00	471.250,00	471.250,00
10	F4L	BE	98.400,00	11.500,00				27.475,00		137.375,00	1,00	137.375,00	137.375,00
11	ILSI	BE	193.450,00	51.500,00				61.237,50		306.187,50	1,00	306.187,50	306.187,50
12	UniBO	IT	75.000,00	7.500,00				20.625,00		103.125,00	1,00	103.125,00	103.125,00
13	WEcR	NL	139.900,00	7.500,00				36.850,00		184.250,00	1,00	184.250,00	184.250,00
14	EIT Food		117.000,00	2.500,00				29.875,00		149.375,00	1,00	149.375,00	149.375,00
15	MUFPP (CDM)	IT	42.750,00	3.000,00				11.437,50		57.187,50	1,00	57.187,50	57.187,50
Total			2.503.150,00	680.849,00	20.000,00	0,00	0,00	795.999,75	0,00	3.999.998,75	1,00	3.999.998,75	3.999.998,75

